

Synthesis of *N*-acetyl pyrazole and its analogues

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Abstract : Chalcones have been very attractive starting compounds in organic chemistry, as they are easy to synthesize with large variability. Chalcones are synthesized by Claisen-Schmidt condensation, which involves cross aldol condensation of suitable aldehydes and ketones by base catalysed or acid catalysed reactions followed by dehydration. So our aim is to construct novel *N*-acetyl pyrazole derivatives 4,5-dihydropyrazole were synthesized starting from α,β -unsaturated ketones under the effect of hydrazine hydrate and phenyl hydrazine. After purification of the target molecules, they were confirmed by various characterization techniques like FT-IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and GC-MS analysis.

Keywords : Chalcones, grinding, hydrazine hydrate, pyrazoles.

Introduction

A variety of heterocyclic compounds occurs widely in nature and is useful in biosynthesis. In recent years the chemistry of fused heterocyclic derivatives has received considerable attention due to their synthetic and effective biological importance. Many plant and animal hormones have aromatic heterocycles as a major component.

Chalcones, natural or synthetic compounds belonging to the flavonoid family have much attention in medicinal chemistry¹ and also serve as predominant intermediates for the synthesis of a large number of heterocyclic systems², also very important as a Michael acceptor in organic synthesis³. These α,β -unsaturated ketones have been extensively studied for their biological activities, including antiparasitic, antitumor, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antitubercular, antifungal, anaesthetic, analgesic and insecticidal activities^{4,5}.

Pyrazoles derivatives like, 5-hydroxy-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles are known to have anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity⁶. Pyrazoles exhibit analgesic⁷, antimicrobial⁸, anti-inflammatory⁹, antihypertensive¹⁰ and hypoglycemic¹¹ activities and appear promising as antiprotozoal and cytotoxic agents¹².

Results and discussion

The synthetic strategy adopted in this work for synthesis of the target compounds, **4a-f** is depicted in eq. (2) using glacial acetic acid as a solvent. The required chalcone precursors **3a-b** were prepared as previously described from our previous literature.

Synthesis of (*E*)-3-alkyl-1-phenylbut-2-en-1-one (**3a,b**).

FT-IR data of compound **4a** shows absorption peak at 1432 cm^{-1} indicates benzene C=C stretching, peak at 1665 cm^{-1} indicates alkene C=C stretching, peak at 1772 cm^{-1} indicates C=O stretching, peaks at 2872 cm^{-1} indicates sp³ C-H stretching. ^1H NMR data of compound, **4a** shows one methyl group at δ 2.04, one methylene at δ 3.83, one -CH proton at δ 4.90, twelve aromatic protons exists between δ 7.1 to 8.4 and one -NH proton at δ 10.2, which confirms the formation of 1-(5-(1*H*-indol-3-yl)-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)ethanone (**4a**). ^{13}C NMR data of compound, **4a** confirms the existence of three aliphatic carbons at δ 22.4, 47.5, 63.7, whereas the aromatic carbons exists at δ 110.4–151.7 and carbonyl group occurs at δ 168.5.

Synthesis of 1-(5,5-dialkyl-3-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)ethanone (**4**).

Experimental

Synthesis of (*E*)-3-alkyl-1-phenylbut-2-en-1-one (**3**) :

An equimolar mixture of acetophenone (2 mmol) and aldehyde (2 mmol) were grinded in basic medium together with pestle and mortar under solvent free condition for 20 min. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature, yielded a yellow solid product. The above said procedure provided products in good to excellent yields with simple and mild reaction conditions. Structures of synthesized compounds were established on the basis of spectral analyses (IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, Mass).

Code	RCHO	RCOR	Time (h)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
3a		Acetophenone	24	74	280
3b		2-Acetonaphthone	24	78	220

Synthesis of 1-(5,5-dialkyl-3-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)ethanone (**4**) :

The corresponding chalcones (**3a-b**) (10 mmol) were refluxed in acetic acid (20 ml) and substituted hydrazine derivatives (40 mmol) for 4 h. The mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice and neutralized by ammonia. The product was washed by cold water and recrystallized from appropriate polar solvents. The obtained compound was characterized by ¹H NMR and FT-IR analysis.

1-(5-(1*H*-Indol-3-yl)-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)ethanone (**4a**, C₂₃H₁₉N₃O) :

Yield 60%; m.p. 182 °C; IR (KBr) : $\bar{\nu}$ 3388.93, 3199.91, 3046.5, 2872.4, 1772.6, 1665.4, 1432.6; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 400 MHz) δ : 2.03 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.83 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH₂), 4.90 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.11 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.18 (1H, s, -CH), 7.32 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.59 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 8.00 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 8.04 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 8.08 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 8.43 (1H, s, -CH), 10.2 (1H, s, -NH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃,

Table 2. Physical data of 1-(5,5-dialkyl-3-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)ethanone (**4a-f**)

Product code	Chalcone (3)	Hydrazine	Time (h)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
4a		Hydrazine hydrate	4	60	182
4b		Phenyl hydrazine	4	69	209
4c		2,4-DNPH	4	74	202
4d		Hydrazine hydrate	4	67	Decomposed 160
4e		Phenyl hydrazine	4	78	135
4f		2,4-DNPH	4	81	187

ppm, 125 MHz) δ : 22.4, 41.6, 63.7, 110.4, 115.4, 116.8, 119.7, 121.7, 123.1, 2 \times 126.2, 126.9, 127.2, 127.4, 2 \times 128.1, 128.2, 128.6, 132.0, 133.6, 136.1, 151.7, 168.5; MS : m/z 353.16 (M^+).

1-(5-(1H-Indol-3-yl)-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)-2-phenylpyrazolidin-1-yl)ethanone (4b, C₂₉H₂₅N₃O) :

Yield 69%; m.p. 209 °C; IR (KBr) : $\bar{\nu}$ 3194.12, 3126.61, 2968.45, 2877.79, 1722.43, 1666.50, 1612.49; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 400 MHz) δ : 2.05 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.42 (2H, t, -CH), 3.90 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH₂), 4.87 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.11 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.12 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.18 (1H, s, -CH), 7.20 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.32 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.39 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.46 (1H, s, -CH), 7.57 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.94 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.97 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 8.02 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 10.2 (1H, s, -NH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 125 MHz) δ : 23.7, 47.3, 64.3, 75.6, 110.4, 2 \times 113.2, 115.5, 116.3, 119.7, 121.6, 122.8, 123.1, 124.6, 125.1, 126.0, 2 \times 127.6, 128.0, 2 \times 129.2, 131.7, 132.6, 133.7, 134.9, 151.5, 170.6; MS : m/z 431.17 (M^+).

1-(2-(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)-5-(1H-indol-3-yl)-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)pyrazolidin-1-yl)ethanone (4c, C₂₉H₂₃N₅O₅) :

Yield 67%; m.p. 160 °C; IR (KBr) : $\bar{\nu}$ 3199.91, 2966.52, 1786.08, 1670.35, 1606.70; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 400 MHz) δ : 2.03 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.42 (2H, t, -CH), 3.90 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH₂), 4.87 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.11 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.16 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.18 (1H, s, -CH), 7.31 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.35 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.46 (1H, s, -CH), 7.55 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.94 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.97 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 8.02 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 8.57 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 9.02 (1H, s, -CH), 10.2 (1H, s, -NH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 125 MHz) δ : 23.5, 47.9, 64.7, 74.6, 110.4, 2 \times 115.5, 116.4, 119.6, 120.5, 121.6, 123.1, 124.5, 125.2, 126.0, 2 \times 127.4, 2 \times 127.6, 128.1, 130.5, 131.8, 132.0, 133.7, 2 \times 134.9, 139.2, 143.2, 170.4; MS : m/z 521.15 (M^+).

1-(5-(1H-Indol-3-yl)-3-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)ethanone (4d, C₁₉H₁₇N₃O) :

Yield 69%; m.p. 209 °C; IR (KBr) : $\bar{\nu}$ 3126.61, 2968.45, 2877.79, 1722.43, 1666.50, 1612.49; ¹H NMR

(CDCl₃, ppm, 400 MHz) δ : 2.03 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.89 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH₂), 4.78 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.11 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.18 (1H, s, -CH), 7.31 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.48 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.52 (2H, t, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.67 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 10.2 (1H, s, -NH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 125 MHz) δ : 23.4, 41.1, 64.1, 110.4, 115.5, 116.2, 119.8, 121.7, 123.1, 127.4, 2 \times 128.2, 2 \times 128.8, 131.0, 132.3, 136.4, 151.7, 168.4; MS : m/z 303.15 (M^+).

1-(5-(1H-Indol-3-yl)-2,3-diphenylpyrazolidin-1-yl)ethanone (4e, C₂₅H₂₃N₃O) :

Yield 78%; m.p. 135 °C; IR (KBr) : $\bar{\nu}$ 2918.30, 2848.86, 1772.58, 1699.29, 1633.71; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 400 MHz) δ : 2.03 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.43 (2H, t, -CH), 3.89 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH₂), 4.86 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 6.90 (1H, t, -CH), 7.11 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.12 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.18 (1H, s, -CH), 7.26 (1H, t, -CH), 7.28 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.31 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.37 (2H, t, -CH), 7.40 (2H, t, -CH), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 10.2 (1H, s, -NH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 125 MHz) δ : 23.6, 47.8, 64.5, 75.2, 110.4, 2 \times 113.2, 115.5, 116.2, 119.8, 121.6, 123.2, 127.4, 2 \times 128.1, 2 \times 128.8, 132.0, 139.4, 151.5, 170.4; MS : m/z 381.17 (M^+).

1-(2-(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)-5-(1H-indol-3-yl)-3-phenylpyrazolidin-1-yl)ethanone (4f, C₂₅H₂₁N₅O₅) :

Yield 81%; m.p. 187 °C; IR (KBr) : $\bar{\nu}$ 2918.30, 1712.79, 1612.49, 1494.33; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 400 MHz) δ : 2.05 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.17 (2H, t, -CH), 3.90 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH₂), 4.87 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.11 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.18 (1H, s, -CH), 7.27 (1H, t, -CH), 7.29 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.32 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.36 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 7.40 (2H, t, -CH), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 8.57 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH), 9.02 (1H, s, -CH), 10.2 (1H, s, -NH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, ppm, 125 MHz) δ : 23.7, 47.9, 64.6, 74.1, 111.1, 115.0, 115.5, 116.2, 119.8, 120.5, 120.7, 123.1, 126.0, 127.4, 2 \times 128.1, 2 \times 128.8, 130.5, 132.0, 134.9, 2 \times 139.4, 143.5, 170.4; MS : m/z 471.16 (M^+).

Conclusion

Synthesis of (*E*)-3-alkyl-1-phenylbut-2-en-1-one (**3**) from acetophenone (**1**) using heteroaldehyde (**2**) in alc.

KOH medium. A series of 4,5-dihydropyrazole (**4**) derivatives bearing acetyl moieties are synthesized from the corresponding chalcones (**3**) were refluxed in acetic acid (20 ml) with substituted hydrazine derivatives. The synthesized target molecules were characterized by FT-IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and Mass spectral analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to VIT University, DST-VIT-FIST, SIF-VIT, VIT management for providing the facilities and fellowships to carry out research work.

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